

ECT2 can identify bona fide tumor suppressors, can serve as a tool for population-based detection of transformation and solid tumors in humans, and has biologic, translational, and clinical applicability in multiple other settings.

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Discussion

- a. Concept: ECT2 induction can be used as a marker for identification of tumor suppressors (genes with bona fide tumor suppressor function).
- b. Together we have been able to use total transcriptional data acquired through whole transcriptome study of primary tumors arising in organs across the human body, including the breast, lung, endometrium, pancreas and cervix to identify ECT2 as a conserved transcriptional element of the solid tumor gene expression signature in humans based on the magnitude and consistent nature of its induction in human cancer (in solid organs).
- c. This is conserved in mouse models of cancer resulting from engineered deficiency of p53, indicating ECT2 was a marker of transformation, a necessary component of transformation that was a proximal consequence of tumor suppressor loss, mutation or disability rather than a gene found to be activated in multiple solid tumor types but less directly associated with genesis of the transformed state.
- d. We validated our discovery of ECT2 as a major solid tumor gene product, in the framework of minimal components of a solid tumor in man, whose induction during transformation could be recapitulated, by studying human cells with engineered deletion, depletion or mutation of established tumor suppressors p53 and Rb1.
- e. We were able to use ECT2 induction as a tool in MSH/MLH mutant genetic background to study using whole transcriptome methods pre-cancer and advanced pre-cancer, to monitor and study transformation in humans at a more precise level than before, compared to techniques currently utilized like historically based identification of dysplastic and advanced dysplastic states, which are based on pathologic microscopic analysis at the level of structural changes in cells and tissues, not changes in messenger RNA induction and quantities.
- f. We were able to identify the onset of transformation in a human with germline mismatch repair deficiency using this framework and set of tools, which includes TK1 induction as a second component of transformation.
- g. Based on our study of transformation in humans, we were able to use whole transcriptome technology to experimentally evaluate loss of function in mismatch repair machinery depletion (MLH/MSH family genes including MLH1, MSH2 and MSH6) *in vitro* to identify a fourth tumor suppressor in humans, MSH2.
- h. Accurate description of the cancer gene expression program is important for development of novel therapeutics and detection methods for prevention of disease, and thus understanding and establishing ECT2 as a component transcriptional feature of the solid tumor transcriptome is important scientifically and medically, not a trivial or politically based discussion. ECT2 was identified in the early 1990s using a cDNA expression library-based screen in 3T3 cells to identify cDNAs with transforming potential using foci formation as a measure of transformation capacity. This indicated that in one cellular context its expression was sufficient to drive transformation *in vitro*.
- i. Apparent sufficiency of ECT2 induction to drive transformation in biologically relevant contexts associated had been initially described by work in the early 1990s was related to but distinctly separate from our discovery and description of ECT2 induction as a component of transformation in solid

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- tissues in man and mice, a direct function of its activation resulting from a multitude of transformative triggers with sufficient potential to activate tumorigenesis (i.e., KRas G12V mutation or p53 R175H mutation, whose ability to serve as a sufficient trigger, driver of transformation that results in formation of a tumor)
- j. Whether findings from the investigators screening in 3T3 cells was a reflection of the strength of the suggested transforming potential of ECT2 as an individual gene, or whether this was instead an accurate reflection of the involvement of ECT2 in transformed contexts, whose expression in a recombinant cellular system could support induction of changes associated with transformation in vitro (in this case foci formation) but whose sole expression is not otherwise sufficient to drive transformation in mammalian tissues (like deletion of a tumor suppressor or mutation of over-expression of an oncogene) was a complex matter.
- k. We do not currently understand ECT2 to be, endogenously expressed, in man or mice, or in its mutant forms found in humans with solid tumors including cancer of the lung, a bona fide oncogene with equivalent transforming potential or capacity as the KRas mutant oncogenes or the BRaf V600E mutant oncogene found in humans with melanoma, whose expression is sufficient to induce progression from benign nevi to a malignant melanoma.
- l. We can determine and describe with confidence that ECT2 is universal transcriptional component (gene signature element) of transformation in humans in solid organs (non-hematopoietic tissues).
- m. Extensive study of total transcription in transformed settings and during the progression from benign to transformed state in vitro and in vivo together indicated that its natural endogenous expression, like during its modulation in the mammalian embryo, or expression of ECT2 in its mutant variant (whose presence in the tumor genome of certain cancer types is described to be a feature of cancer progression, indicating its ability (albeit not sufficiency) to support as one of many genes products with oncogene-like properties, whose mutation is observed as a function of tumor development (disease progression) was essentially different from that of the transformative capacities of mutant oncogenes, over-expressed oncogenes like Myc induction driven by Ig mu regulatory elements, or that of tumor suppressor genes that acquire transformation potential through de novo or germline acquired mutation (Rb1 in retinoblastoma), or deletion-induced loss of tumor suppressor genes.
- n. This is distinctly separate and distinguishable from the properties and characteristic of oncogenes and tumor suppressors, like mutation of p53, deficiency of APC in the colon, or germline mutation of mismatch repair gene MSH2 in humans.
- o. Genes like ECT2, whose mutation might support disease progression or favor positive clonal selection during tumor development as one of a community or network of genes, are different from oncogenes like KRas G12V, BRaf V600E, or dominant negative mutations like p53 R175H in two ways: the relative capacity of the gene to serve itself as an individual driver of transformation, its general transformative potential, as well as the point in cancer development at which the genes expression change or mutation becomes relevant in the tumors existence. Genes whose biological functions endows them with tumor-supportive or oncogene-like

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properties are generally appreciable in their mutant, variant or silenced/activated forms at a chronologically distinct point in tumorigenesis from genes (bona fide tumor suppressors and oncogenes) whose mutation, variation, or expression change is sufficient to activate tumorigenesis and properly establish a tumor.

- p. Mutations like that found in genes that have cooperative functions in cancer progression, like ECT2, that are not understood to be sufficient to initiate tumorigenesis in vivo and in vitro as an individual gene product, who are described (errantly) in some literature based on their identification in mutant form in tumor genomes, as an oncogene (e.g., another case, LKB2, whose mutation is well described to support cancer progression, cooperating with tumor suppressor loss to drive disease progression, resulting in its (errant) description as a tumor suppressor, but whose mutation or altered expression does not serve as the initial driver of tumorigenesis, as do bona fide tumor suppressors p53 or Rb1; these oncogene like molecules with transformation supporting qualities are generally not present in their mutant or altered form until after establishment of the primary tumor.
- q. In summary, we find that ECT2-labeling based imaging will be an extraordinarily useful tool in the human population for cancer detection and early prevention of disease (with development of safe, immunoglobulin or small molecule based ECT2 protein detection agents) whose magnitude of induction provides unique sensitivity and specificity to detect transformation, and thus resolution that far surpasses that of currently used cancer detection/screening methods in the community such as mammography,

which relies on radiologic identification of structural changes early in disease, much later than the time at which ECT2 is present in adequate quantities to prevent progression to this state.

- r. A second clinical application of ECT2 based imaging in humans with cancer (solid tumors) is sensitive and specific imaging of metastasis to distinguish tumor from normal tissues in any distant organ site to which the primary tumor has metastasized, enabling the surgeon and medical team to treat metastasis cases that would otherwise be considered inoperable, like brain metastasis cases, with multiple locations in the organ, or in organs in which the metastatic tumor(s) is/are difficult to distinguish from the normal tissue or are diffuse in nature.
- s. Separate from its ability and promise to serve as a marker for cancer detection at the population level, the intimate relationship we have demonstrated between transcriptional induction of ECT2 and activation of the transformed state culminating in establishment of disease in humans with cancer (formation of the tumor), occurring at quantitatively appreciable magnitude (assessable by differential transcriptome analysis) and occurring rapidly, immediately following transformation has been initiated by the proximal trigger, demonstrates its capacity to serve as a transcriptional measure of a genes ability to serve as an oncogene or tumor suppressor, or a transcriptional tool, reagent that can correctly identify a tumor suppressor or oncogene, like that of a bona fide oncogene (with sufficient transformative potential) that when over-expressed, mutated, or present as a gene fusion resulting from structural changes in the chromosomes- as an oncogene, or in the case of a bona fide tumor suppressor, mutation, deletion, or otherwise disability/impairment (e.g.,

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- epigenetic silencing) is sufficient to induce cancer.
- t. As an essential component of the solid tumor gene expression program, ECT2 induction serves as a method of studying and defining the essential components of the tumor transcriptome, to measure induction and maintenance of transformation in the tumor, to compare relative induction of transformation between experimental systems or cancer types, to use precise quantities measured by quantitative PCR or transcriptome technology (microarray, RNA-sequencing or multiplexed PCR based methods) to dissect and define important questions in cancer like understanding what confers tissue restricted oncogenic capacity to specific oncogenic mutants, and to study the genesis of cancer in human cells and in genetically engineered solid tumor models (with an ECT2-specific antibody or using a transgenic cell line or animal model with engineered knock-in of ECT2 fluorescent protein fusion), enabling study of the development of cancer in vitro and in vivo with unrivaled resolution (precision and clarity) by enabling monitoring of transformation in real time.
- u. This has allowed us to discover the presence of important transcriptional changes that are essential elements of transformation. One recent example was the discovery of homeobox transcription factor activation by oncogene mutation and tumor suppressor mutation. In an existing, full developed tumor, we found that silencing expression of a single homeobox gene, PAX8, resulted in significant loss of ECT2 expression, indicating both that the homeobox was an essential element or component of the solid tumor gene expression program, and that its continued presence was sufficient to maintain a threshold of activity to support maintenance of a transformed state, as its engineered depletion was sufficient to collapse the transformed state of the tumor.
- v. We are currently using systems biologic methods to more closely understand the relationship between ECT2 and transformation, which appears to reflect a cell biologic requirement for ECT2 during cell division at the plasma membrane.